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nonical factors had a significant correlation ($p < 0.001$). When observing the factor's structure, the highest correlation on the left set was for anthropometric parameters – body height (0.95), body mass (0.79), standing reach (0.91), wingspan (0.85), and hand length (0.62). On the right set, the highest correlation with the first factor was noted for total rebounds (0.51), defensive rebounds (0.41), offensive rebounds (0.62), and blocks (0.61). **CONCLUSION:** Anthropometric parameters seem to be an important factor in both the defensive and offensive phases of the basketball game on post positions.

O48

Examining the Association Between Physical Activity, Burnout Symptoms and Academic Performance among Health Sciences Students from Eight South-East European Countries

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PURPOSE: The aim of this study was to examine the association between level of physical activity (PA), burnout symptoms and academic performance among health sciences students. **METHODS:** A cross-sectional study was conducted April-September in 2023 on a sample of 3473 students from 69 faculties in 8 countries (Slovenia, Croatia, Bosnia, Serbia, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Romania and Greece) using online survey. **RESULTS:** Sufficient weekly levels of PA (≥ 600 MET) were reported by 86.7% of students, 56.5% students had moderate-level of PA (600- 3000 MET) and 30.2% had high-level PA (≥ 3000 MET). The highest level of PA had students from Faculty of Medicine University of Montenegro (92.9%), while students from Faculty of Pharmacy, University Ovidius in Constanța (Romania) had the lowest PA (64.7%). Only male gender and higher years of study were significant positive predictors of higher PA levels. Higher PA levels were associated with higher academic performance. Sufficient PA was the positive predictor of academic achievement ($\beta: 0.117$, 95%CI: 1.313–2.347). Students from Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Sarajevo (Bosnia) had the highest level of physical, cognitive and emotional burnout, while students from Faculty of Medicine University of Montenegro had the lowest. Higher PA levels were associated with significantly lower burnout symptoms. Sufficient PA was the negative predictor of physical ($\beta: -0.074$, 95%CI: -2.795–-1.063), cognitive ($\beta: -0.094$, 95%CI: -3.021–-1.45) and emotional burnout ($\beta: -0.067$, 95%CI: -1.456–-0.493). **CONCLUSION:** The results indicate that it is necessary to implement appropriate programs to increase PA in the student population in order to prevent burnout and enhance academic performance of students.

O49

Functional movement screen differences between two growth-sensitive period groups of various team sport athletes

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Functionality in physical exercise or sport can be regarded as a capability to perform numerous movements without pain or any limiting factor which could compromise the end result. One way to assess function is through Functional movement screen (FMS) by interpreting its composite score. Besides training, it is considered that active growth of an athlete can have various impact on motoric and functional development. When it comes to FMS differences between sports, age groups and gender, plenty of research has been carried out, but there is a scarce data revealing differences between growth-sensitive

periods. **PURPOSE** of this study is to show difference between two growth-sensitive period groups in composite FMS score and their result distribution. **METHODS:** Study included 563 athletes (age 16.7 ± 2.04) from several team sports, divided into two groups based on their growth period. The instrument used was standard FMS battery which included seven tests and the final composite score was calculated. For data analysis t-test for independent samples was performed. **RESULTS:** Statistically significant t score was obtained and amounts $t = -2.953$. Rank order distribution shows higher frequency percentage favoring older group in trunk stability (45.63% of athletes got the score of 3), shoulder mobility (51.09%), active leg raise (49.45%) and inline lunge (49.19%). **CONCLUSION:** Physical growth can impact athletes mobility, trunk stability and inline lunge pattern.

O50

Are physical literacy and physical activity levels correlated in children aged 9-10 years?

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Physical literacy (PL) is described as the motivation, confidence, physical competence, knowledge and understanding to value and engage in a physically active health lifestyle. It has been hypothesized that engaging in physical activity (PA) is associated with possessing PL, but studies rarely examined the problem in preadolescent children. **PURPOSE:** The aim of this research was to determine the possible associations between PL and level of PA in preadolescent children. **METHODS:** The sample comprised children from Split, Croatia ($n = 97$, 48 girls, 9-10 years of age). The PL was evaluated by PLAYself questionnaire and PA levels as assessed using the "Physical Activity Questionnaire for Older Children" (PAQ-C). Differences between genders, and age groups (3rd and 4th grade of elementary school) were established by 2-way analysis of variance ANOVA. Pearson's correlations between PAQ-C and PL were calculated for total sample, and separately for each gender, and age-group. **RESULTS:** ANOVA calculations did not reveal significant effects for gender (F -test = 1.00, $p = 0.39$), or age group (F -test = 0.46, $p = 0.50$). The PL and PAQ-C were not significantly correlated in total sample of participants, in boys (mixed ages), and in 3rd graders (mixed genders). Significant correlations between PAQ-C and PL were found for girls (mixed ages; 16% of the common variance, $p < 0.01$), and for 4th grade children (mixed genders; 17% of the common variance, $p < 0.01$). **CONCLUSION:** The significant correlations between PA and PL in girls, and in 4th graders could be attributed to the differences in participation in structured and unstructured activities. In brief, PA in these groups is primarily result of their participation in structured physical activities such as organized sports or physical education, which simultaneously result in higher PL.

O51

The Impact of a Combined Exercise Model on Certain Dimensions of Exercisers' Anthropological Status

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Numerous studies have explored the impact of various group exercise programs on alterations in the anthropological dimensions of participants. **PURPOSE:** This study was conducted to investigate the effects of a combined model group exercise program on body composition, explosive power, and balance. **METHODS:** The sample consisted of 22 participants engaged in a three-times-weekly, 60-minute exercise